

Preparation of 2,2'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyl-5,5'-dinitrodiphenyl Sulphide

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2-Hydroxy-5-nitroacetophenone gave a sulphide (I) when allowed to react with thionyl chloride in presence of finely divided copper. On nitration in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid, sulphide (I) gave picric acid. The ketonic group, situated in the *ortho* position to the hydroxyl group, is usually replaced by a nitro group during nitration'. Out of the three nitro groups in picric acid, the one *para* to the -OH group is that which was already present in the ketonic nucleus. Of the two nitro groups that are in the *ortho* positions to the -OH group, one has come in the place of the ketonic group and hence the other must have replaced the sulphur atom. Hence it was concluded that the two aromatic nuclei were joined through the sulphur atom in position *ortho* to -OH and *meta* to -COMe and -NO₂ groups.

Sulphide (I) is isomeric with 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxy-5,5'-dinitrodiphenyl sulphide (II), which has been prepared by nitration of 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphide'. Attempts to prepare sulphide (II) by the interaction of 2-hydroxy-3-nitroacetophenone and thionyl chloride in presence of finely divided copper met with no success as the ketone did not react.

2,2'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetyl-5,5'-dinitrodiphenyl Sulphide (I).—Thionyl chloride (5 ml) was added to a mixture of 2-hydroxy-5-nitroacetophenone (1g.), copper (2g.), and dry ether (15 ml). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. Next day, it was heated on a boiling water bath to remove excess of thionyl chloride and ether. The dry residue was extracted with excess of ethanol from which a yellowish substance crystallised. It decomposed at 175°. (Found: S, 8.35. C₁₆H₁₂O₈N₂S requires S, 8.16%).

The *diacetate* of (I) was obtained by boiling it with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine; m.p. 168-70°. (Found: S, 6.50. C₂₀H₁₆O₁₀N₂S requires S, 6.72%).

Bis-2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of (I) melted at 220-22°. (Found: S, 4.11. C₂₈H₂₀O₁₄N₁₀S requires S, 4.25%).

Formation of 2,4,6-Trinitrophenol.—The sulphide (I) (0.5g.) was added to a mixture of HNO₃ (conc., 15ml) and H₂SO₄ (conc., 15 ml) and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. Next day, it was diluted with ice water and the solution was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution gave a yellow substance which melted at 120°. It gave test for nitrogen but did not answer test for sulphur. It showed no lowering in m.p. when mixed with a genuine specimen of picric acid.

Interaction of Thionyl Chloride and 2-Hydroxy-3-nitroacetophenone.—Thionyl chloride (5 ml) was added to a mixture of 2-hydroxy-3-nitroacetophenone (1 g.), copper powder (2 g.), and dry ether (30 ml). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. Next day, it was heated under reflux on a boiling water bath for about an hour. Most of the ketone was recovered unchanged. The chlorides of sulphur were without any action on 2-hydroxy-3-nitroacetophenone.

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